

plot design with N in the main plots and sources in the subplots.

Seedlings of Lalat (Obs 677/IR2071//Vikram/W1263, 130d duration group) were transplanted on 22 Jan. All plots received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha with all the LGU, NCU, RPU, SCU, and 1/3 the PU at transplanting. All the USG was placed 7 cm deep at 10 d after transplanting (DT). The additional PU was applied in equal splits at 20 DT and at panicle initiation.

Yields increased significantly with increasing N up to 112.5 kg N/ha (Table 1), although yield response (kg grain/kg N) and apparent N recovery values (Table 2) were highest at 37.5 kg N. Yields with USG and SCU were equal and significantly superior to those with other N sources. USG at 75 kg N/ha was the best treatment, as is reflected in yield response and apparent N recovery. □

Table 1. Grain yield with urea-based N sources. Bhubaneswar, India, 1986 dry season.

Nitrogen dose (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)						
	PU	USG	LGU	NCU	RPU	SCU	Mean
0	2.2	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.1	2.4	2.2
37.5	3.4	4.3	3.5	3.9	3.9	3.7	3.8
75.0	4.5	5.5	4.4	4.3	3.9	5.0	4.6
112.5	5.5	5.5	4.7	5.1	5.3	6.2	5.4
150.0	5.6	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.3	5.5	5.5
Mean	4.2	4.6	4.0	4.2	4.1	4.5	4.3
LSD (0.05) N:0.6, Source: 0.3. Sources at fixed N: 0.7 and N at the same or different source: 0.9							

Table 2. Yield response and apparent N recovery with urea-based N sources. Bhubaneswar, India, 1986 dry season.

Nitrogen dose (kg/ha)	Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Source		
			Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Apparent N recovery (%)	
37.5	41.6	51.4	PU	28.0	44.7
75.0	31.7	39.3	USG	38.1	54.2
112.5	28.0	42.7	LGU	26.6	32.6
150.0	21.7	40.2	NCU	30.1	41.9
			RPU	28.6	39.5
			SCU	33.1	47.5

Effect of urea supergranule (USG) on grain yield of varieties of different durations

S. V. Subbaiah and S. K. Sharma, Agronomy Department, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh, India

We studied the influence of USG on varieties of different durations in controlled irrigated experiments 1984-

85. Recommended P, K, and Zn were applied before field puddling, N was applied as per treatment. The soil was a Vertisol type with pH 8.2, CEC 49.2 meq/ 100 g soil, 0.09% total N, and 5 ppm available P.

Short-duration (95-105 d) IET7564, IET7613, IET7614, and IET7566 were evaluated with 90 kg N/ ha using USG placement and prilled urea split application. Source of N was not significant (3.94.4 t/ha).

In longduration (150-165 d) IET5897, IET5890, IET5656, Jagannath, Phalgun, and Pankaj, 90 kg N/ ha as urea best split was superior or equal to USG placement at 7 d after transplanting (DT). Yields with 3/4 N as USG at 7 DT + 1/4 N as prilled urea at panicle initiation were significantly greater than yields with prilled urea best split (Table 1).

Medium-duration Rasi responded better to USG (90 kg N/ha) than to prilled urea and other coated materials (Table 2). □

Table 1. Mean grain yield of irrigated six long-duration varieties with USG and split applications of prilled urea. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1984	1985
Best split (prilled urea)	5.8	4.9
Four splits (prilled urea)	5.3	4.6
USG at 7 DT	5.5	5.1
1/4 N as prilled urea (basal) + 3/4 N as USG at 28 DT	-	5.1
3/4 N as USG at 7 DT + 1/4 N as prilled urea at panicle initiation	-	5.3
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.2
CV (%)	7.1	6.8

Table 2. Effect of modified urea materials on grain yield of Rasi. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984 kharif.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Urea best split	4.6
USG at 7 DT	5.8
Mussoorie-phos-coated urea	4.8
Gypsum-coated urea	4.8
Neem cake-coated urea	4.4
Urea 4 equal splits (1/4 N basal + 1/4 N before panicle initiation + 1/4 N after panicle initiation + 1/4 N panicle stage)	4.5
Compost + USG (1/2 N as USG)	4.8
CD (0.05)	0.8
CV (%)	9.4

Mussoorie rock phosphate (MRP) effects on yield

Badrinath, A.M. Krishnappa, P.S. Herle, B.N. Patil, N.A.J. Gowda, and K.B. Rao, Agricultural Research Station, Mangalore 575002, India

MRP is an indigenous fertilizer material suitable for acid soils; it slowly and continuously releases available P.

We studied its availability to rice variety Phalgun in a field experiment